

A STUDY OF DECISION MAKING OF HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract:

Decision making is one of the most important life skills. While making correct, timely, accurate and appropriate decisions lead to positive changes in one's life, making incorrect decisions may have a negative impact. It is an important issue to examine what in high school teachers have about the decision-making ability to be achieved in what qualities of students should have for this skill. The aim of this research is to examine decision making of high school teachers according to variables as gender, status, residential of area, religion, mode of management, location of school, nature of school, teaching experience, marital status and type of family. Working group consists of 272 females and 157 males, totally 429 high school teachers, in vellore district in Tamil nadu. The data were collected from sampled teachers using a standardized self-administered questionnaire and analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t-test and F test by analyzed using SPSS Version 20. The findings revealed that the there is no significant difference between high school teachers towards decision making of samples such as gender, status, residential of area, religion, mode of management, location of school, nature of school, teaching experience, marital status and type of family.

Introduction:

Decision making is defined as the assessment of two or more options and the ability to choose between them (Budak, 2000). Preference and choice making are the most important components of decision-making concept in the definitions in literature. The individual passes in his daily life positions require him to make a decision or more, The process of decision-making is an important process in every moment of our lives, which requires mastery of the individual to some of the skills that help in decision-making such as social skills, which is an essential requirement and a means help the individual to communicate and engage in social interactions with others, success in making many of the decisions depends on how the individual confidence in his ability and self-efficacy, which help him to go ahead on those decisions. self- efficiency contribute in determining the initiative behavior on him, it is also linked to social skills, which may affect the quality of decision-making, where the individuals who are characterized by high self-efficiency and high social skills tend to take decisions with high quality more than individuals with low self-efficiency and low social skills, in other words, when the ability is equal between some individuals, those who believe in their ability to do the work, they are more likely achieve it more successfully than those who do not believe so (Bandura, 1986).

Decision-making is the ability to show behaviors that appeal to the individual's mood and logic and that also ensure individual's social acceptance and attainment of respectable results (Karaçay, 2015). The decision-making process is a cognitive process that entails choosing the appropriate behavior with a tendency (preference) to satisfy a need as soon as it arises and to eliminate accompanying tension (Kuzgun, 1992). Considering the definitions made on the subject, decision-making process, which is defined as the evaluation of the choices or making preferences, also seems to be regarded as a process based on social values. The purpose of the individual in the decision-making process can be expressed as to find the optimal solution in accordance with his/her own purpose, values, goals and needs.

Moreover, the decision-making process requires the availability of the social environment in which the individual lives, the sum of skills available in the decision-maker, as well as the required objectives to achieve behind the decision making. (ElDesoki, 1998) It can be said that self-efficacy has a positive impact on social skills, which is to deal with others in the community, as well as decision-making contribute to effective role in providing psychological support to the individual. In spite of the difficulties faced by the students, some trying to search for causes that help in decision-making and the procedural definition of social skill is the total score you get on the scale used in this current study. The current study tried to identify the level of self-efficacy and social skills and their relationship to the quality of decision-making.

Teachers can take a larger role in the overall success of the school when they become committed to active participate in the decision-making process. A number of researchers have studied the relationships of teachers' increased involvement in decision-making with a number of important school variables. In relation to this, Smylie (1996) stated that participation improves teachers opportunities in acquiring new knowledge and insights.

One of the reasons for involving teachers in decision-making is that it improves the overall performance of the school. Involving teachers in decision-making process is a means to increase the productivity and efficiency of an educational organization. Pashiards (1994) in this regard, explained that

increasing the level of teacher participation in decision-making process makes school policy and management more responsive to societal needs. In sum, the participation of teachers in decision-making pertinent to any aspect of school operation has a positive impact on school performance. School principals are therefore, expected to encourage teachers to actively participate in decision-making so that informed decision can be made at school level.

Operational Definition of Term Used:

The quality of decision-making: the ability to make a good positive decision that achieves the set goals at the lowest cost and in a timely manner. It is defined procedurally by the score obtained by the student by answering the paragraphs of the quality of the decision-making scale.

Purpose of the Study:

The purpose of this study is to assess the desired and actual levels of teachers' participation in decision-making in the high schools of Vellore District, Tamil nadu.

Methodology:

Normative survey method was followed. The present study is based on decision making of high school teachers.

Sample:

The sample consists of 429 of high school teacher selected from the schools of Vellore district. Out of which 272 females and 157 males. The sample was collected by using random sampling technique

Description of the Decision Making Scale:

The decision making tool contains 23 items and all are positive items. It has been prepared by Susanne G. Scott. The tool contains 23 statements where responses can be used to measure the decision making of high school teachers. Each statement has to be answered by choosing any one of the alternatives such as Strongly agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly disagree (1).

Data Analysis:

The data collected from the sample population were systematically coded, tabulated and organized for analysis. The coded data were entered in to Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 20 for analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to describe the data. In addition, t-test and F test was used to see if there is statistically significant difference between teachers actual and desired level of participation in decision-making.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the significant difference between decision making of high school teachers with respect to gender.
- ✓ To find out the significant difference between decision making of high school teachers with respect to status.
- ✓ To find out the significant difference between decision making of high school teachers with respect to residential area.
- ✓ To find out the significant difference between decision making of high school teachers with respect to religion.
- ✓ To find out the significant difference between decision making of high school teachers with respect to mode of management.
- ✓ To find out the significant difference between decision making of high school teachers with respect to location of school.
- ✓ To find out the significant difference between decision making of high school teachers with respect to nature of school.
- ✓ To find out the significant difference between decision making of high school teachers with respect to teaching experience.
- ✓ To find out the significant difference between decision making of high school teachers with respect to marital status.
- ✓ To find out the significant difference between decision making of high school teachers with respect to family type.

Hypotheses of the Study:

There is no significant difference in decision making of high school teachers with respect to following sub samples

- Gender : Male / Female
- Status : Temporary / Permanent
- Residential area : Rural / Urban
- Religion : Hindu / Muslim / Christian
- Mode of management : Government / Private / Aided
- Location of school : Rural / Urban
- Nature of school : Boys / Girls / Co education

Teaching experience : Below 5 years / 6-10 years / 11-15 years / Above 16 years
 Marital status : Married / Unmarried
 Type of family : Nuclear / Joint

Analysis of Data:

Table 1: Difference between Male and Female High School Teachers in their Decision Making

Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'-value	Remarks
Male	157	92.50	11.952	0.505	NS
Female	272	93.10	11.465		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between male and female high school teachers in their decision making.

Table 2: Difference between Permanent and Temporary Status High School Teachers in their Decision Making

Status	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'-value	Remarks
Permanent	318	92.74	11.746	0.455	NS
Temporary	111	93.30	11.353		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between permanent and temporary high school teachers in their decision making.

Table 3: Difference between Rural and Urban High School Teachers in their Decision Making

Residential Area	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'-value	Remarks
Rural	269	92.67	12.136	0.504	NS
Urban	160	93.24	10.768		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between rural and urban high school teachers in their decision making.

Table 4: Difference among Hindu, Christian and Muslim High School Teachers Religion in their Decision Making

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	Mean Square Value	Calculated 'F'-value	Remarks
Between	74.298	202.949	0.273	NS
Within	57866.639	181.204		

(At 5% level of significance for 2,426 df the table value of 'F' is 3.03)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among Hindu, Christian and Muslim high school teachers in their decision making.

Table 5: Difference among Government, Aided and Private High School Teachers in their Decision Making

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	Mean Square Value	Calculated 'F'-value	Remarks
Between	411.095	205.548	1.522	NS
Within	57529.842	135.047		

(At 5% level of significance for 2,426 df the table value of 'F' is 3.03)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among government, aided and private high school teachers in their decision making.

Table 6: Difference between Rural and Urban High School Teachers in their Decision Making

Location of School	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'-value	Remarks
Rural	237	93.10	11.750	0.428	NS
Urban	192	92.61	11.517		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between rural and urban high school teachers in their decision making.

Table 7: Difference Among the of Boys', Girls' and Co-Education High School Teachers in their Decision Making

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	Mean Square Value	Calculated 'F'-value	Remarks
Between	328.199	164.100	1.213	NS
Within	57612.738	135.241		

(At 5% level of significance for 2,426 df the table value of 'F' is 3.03)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among boys', girls' and co-education high school teachers in their decision making.

Table 8: Difference among High School Teachers Having Teaching Experience below 5 Years, 6 To 10 Years, 11 to 15 Years and Above 16 Years in their Decision Making

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	Mean Square Value	Calculated 'F'- value	Remarks
Between	650.781	216.927	1.609	NS
Within	57290.156	134.800		

(At 5% level of significance for 3,425 df the table value of 'F' is 3.03)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among high school teachers having teaching experience below 5 years, 6 to 10 years, 11 to 15 years and above 16 years in their decision making.

Table 9: Difference between Married and Unmarried High School Teachers in their Decision Making

Marital Status	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'- value	Remarks
Married	350	93.06	11.811	0.695	NS
Unmarried	79	92.10	10.859		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between married and unmarried high school teachers in their decision making.

Table 10: Difference between Nuclear and Joint Family High School Teachers in their Decision Making

Family type	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't'- value	Remarks
Nuclear	261	92.48	11.856	0.902	NS
Joint	168	93.51	11.290		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between nuclear and joint family high school teachers in their decision making.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference between male and female high school teachers in their decision making.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference between permanent and temporary high school teachers in their decision making.
- ✓ It is found that that there is no significant difference between rural and urban high school teachers in their decision making.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference among Hindu, Christian and Muslim high school teachers in their decision making.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference among government, aided and private high school teachers in their decision making.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference between rural and urban high school teachers in their decision making.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference among boys', girls' and co-education high school teachers in their decision making
- ✓ It is found that that there is no significant difference among high school teachers having teaching experience below 5 years, 6 to 10 years, 11 to 15 years and above 16 years in their decision making.
- ✓ It is found that there is no significant difference between married and unmarried high school teachers in their decision making.
- ✓ It is found that that there is no significant difference between nuclear and joint family high school teachers in their decision making.

Recommendation:

In light of the findings of the current study, the researcher recommends the following: further studies aim to identify other variables associated with the quality of decision-making. The necessity to work to create an academic climate is reassuring because of its positive effect on the acquisition of the teachers various skills to establish development courses for students for the development of their level in the decision-making. The participation of teachers in decision-making process is crucial for the betterment of the school performance. Hence, the school management body should devise strategies by which teachers can participate more in the decision-making process. In order to devise such strategies, the researchers recommend further study to identify major reasons for low participation of teachers in decision-making process in schools.

Conclusion:

It was clear from the findings of this study that teachers' level of involvement in decision-making was low. This implies that decision-making process in the schools was centralized and decisions are made in the schools with a lesser amount of input from teachers. Furthermore, in the sampled schools, teachers desired more involvement in decision-making than they actually used to involve. This means that schools did not provide teachers with enough opportunity to participate in decision-making though they did desired most. This entails that the decision-making process in the studied schools was not participatory, and efforts made by school management to influence teachers' actual involvement in decision-making was not satisfactory.

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